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D2.7 Conceptual Model and Reference Architecture V2

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Abbreviations

API	Application Programming Interface
AWS	Amazon Web Services
BDV	Big Data Value
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
CRISP-DM	Cross-Industry Standard Process for Data Mining
CSV	Comma Separated Values
CLI	Command Line Interface
DB	DataBase
DL	Deep Learning
EC	European Commission
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ETL	Extract, Transform, and Load
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
HPC	Cloud and High-Performance Computing
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
IaaS	Infrastructure-as-a-Service
IdP	Identity Provider
IM	Instant Messaging
KDD	Knowledge Discovery in Databases
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ML	Machine Learning
NER	Named-Entity Recognition
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OIDC	OpenID Connect
PaaS	Platform-as-a-Service
RA	Reference Architecture
SHAP	SHapley Additive exPlanations
SSH	Secure Shell Protocol
TOSCA	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications
VM	Virtual Machine
VO	Virtual Organisation
VPME	Virtualized Policy Management Environment

WP	Work Package
XAI	eXplainable AI
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

Executive summary

AI4PublicPolicy is a joint effort of policy makers and Cloud/AI experts to unveil AI potential for automated, transparent and citizen-centric development of public policies. To this end, the project will deliver, validate, demonstrate and promote the AI4PublicPolicy platform for automated, scalable, transparent and citizen-centric policy management based on unique AI technologies.

AI4PublicPolicy will provide public authorities, public administrators and other policy making stakeholders with a complete environment for AI-based policy making. Policy makers will be able to design, develop, deploy, validate and fine-tune data-driven, evidence-based policies from a single-entry point.

The AI4PublicPolicy Policy Making Process leverages on the CRISP-DM methodology to address the following objectives:

- Provide a data-driven, AI-based and evidence-based approach
- Promote and facilitate the collaboration between Policy Makers and AI Experts
- Involve citizens and other stakeholders in the Policy evaluation and optimization
- Boost the acceptance of the policies presenting and explaining the Policy development outcomes
- Reuse and share the Policy development models and Datasets across different domains and countries

The AI4PublicPolicy Reference Architecture takes into account and addresses the following concerns of the BDV Reference Model:

- Data Analytics
- Data Protection
- Data Processing Architectures
- Data management
- Cloud and High-Performance Computing
- Data sharing platforms
- Cybersecurity and Trust

The components of the AI4PublicPolicy Reference Architecture are divided into three main subsystems or pillars: Reusable and Interoperable Datasets (Policies and Dataset Collection and Management, Semantic Interoperability, Cross Country Interoperability, Datasets and Policies Catalogue), Policy Transparency and Trust (Explainable AI (XAI), Policy Explainability and Interpretation, AI Security and AutoML) and Policy Extraction and Evaluation (Text and Sentiment Analysis, Policy Extraction, Policy Evaluation and Optimization and Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME)).

The AI4PublicPolicy platform is built on top of the multi-layered EOSC Compute Platform. Its main layers are: Federated Resource Providers layer, the Compute and Data Federation layer, the Platforms layer and the vertical Service Management Tools layer.

This deliverable describes the second version of the AI4PublicPolicy reference architecture, the first version was presented in deliverable D2.6. Although the components remain the same, some of them have been updated after they have been evaluated by the pilots.

The components and the Reference Architecture have been validated towards both the Conceptual Model, describing how the components interact to fulfil the AI-based Policy Making Process in the main high-level scenarios, and the Pilots user stories reported in deliverable D2.1, mapping the components to the needs of each user story.

1 Introduction

1.1 The AI4PublicPolicy Project

AI4PublicPolicy is a joint effort of policy makers and Cloud/AI experts to unveil AI’s potential for automated, transparent and citizen-centric development of public policies. To this end, the project will deliver, validate, demonstrate and promote a novel Open Cloud platform (i.e., AI4PublicPolicy platform) for automated, scalable, transparent and citizen-centric policy management based on unique AI technologies. The AI4PublicPolicy platform will be an Open Virtualized Policy Management Environment (VPME) that will provide fully-fledged policy development/management functionalities based on AI technologies such as Machine Learning (ML), Deep Learning (DL), NLP and chatbots, while leveraging citizens’ participation and feedback. It will support the entire policy development lifecycle, based on technologies for the extraction, simulation, evaluation and optimization of interoperable and reusable public policies, with emphasis on citizen-centric policies development and optimization through the realization of citizen-oriented feedback loops. AI4PublicPolicy will complement public policy development functionalities with the ever-important process reengineering and organization transformation activities towards ensuring the effective transition from legacy policy development models to emerging AI-based policy making.

The AI4PublicPolicy VPME will be integrated with EOSC with a dual objective. First to facilitate access to the Cloud and HPC resources of EOSC/EGI that are required to enable the project’s AI tools, second to boost the sustainability and wider use of the project’s developments. AI4PublicPolicy’s business plan for sustaining, expanding and commercializing the AI tools and the VPME is based on the development of a community of interested and engaged stakeholders (i.e., public authorities and other policy makers) around the project’s platform.

Figure 1. AI4PublicPolicy methodological approach

1.2 Description of WP2

Work Package 2 (WP2) is a central technical work package in the AI4PublicPolicy project. Work Package 2 is divided in a set of major tasks: define the definition of the AI4PublicPolicy architecture (Task 2.5), identify the technical requirements, review standards and regulations (Task 2.2), analyse

the policy making process (Task 2.6) and identify data models of the data sets to be utilized in AI4PublicPolicy.

The objectives of WP2 are to:

- Specify the overall architecture for the AI4PublicPolicy platform by identifying components, their functionalities and interconnection, ensuring their coherency with the requirements and global architecture.
- Identify and track end user and technical requirements provided by the use case partners and the technical contributors of AI4PublicPolicy.
- Review the standards and regulations and identify appropriate ones that need to be monitored and followed in the project.
- Analyse the policy making processes to ensure that the outcomes of the project address and enhance/improve these processes, while reducing the bottlenecks in public administration and ensuring high quality and adoption of results.
- Define the data models of the datasets to be utilized for the development, training and actual utilization of the AI models and algorithms of AI4PublicPolicy.
- Define the co-creation. Relevant activities will be regularly reported in D2.8, in-line with the description of the deliverable.

1.3 Purpose and scope of the deliverable

This deliverable addresses the first of the WP2 objectives reported above, presenting the Conceptual Model for AI-based Policy Making and the Reference Architecture for the AI4PublicPolicy platform.

1.4 Structure of the deliverable

This document is comprised of the following chapters:

- The first section of the document presents an introduction to the project and the document.
- The second section of the document presents the Conceptual Model for AI-based Policy Making.
- The Reference Architecture for the AI4PublicPolicy platform is presented in the third section.
- The fourth section of the document presents the result of the validation of the RA towards the user stories provided for the different pilots.
- The fifth section of the document describes the main scenarios of the AI-based Policy Making.
- The document includes a sixth section with the conclusions of the document.

2 Conceptual Model

AI4PublicPolicy VPME aims to provide public authorities, public administrators and other policy making stakeholders with a complete environment for AI-based policy making, as shown later in Figure 2. Policy makers will be able to design, develop, deploy, validate and fine-tune data-driven, evidence-based policies from a single-entry point.

As a starting point they will provide data and policy information to the VPME. Accordingly, they will be able to use the AI tools in order to extract data-driven insights (e.g., Policy Recommendations, Policy Simulations). At the same time, they will be supported by AutoML techniques, while they will also have the opportunity of executing the XAI tools towards easing the interpretation and presentation of the policies to relevant stakeholders.

The project’s policy development approach will be local actors’ centric: local actors (citizens, businesses and other actors) will be actively engaged in the development, validation and evaluation of the policies and their feedbacks, obtained through public channels and interfaces (e.g. social media for implicit feedback, surveys, applications of local authorities for explicit feedback), will be analysed and taken into account in the development of the policies, as well as in their optimization.

As shown in Figure 2, the VPME will also enable policy makers to repurpose and reuse policy models and datasets in different policy development contexts and applications. This will be boosted by the fact that the VPME will centralize access to all the different policy models and datasets through the EOSC portal/marketplace.

Figure 2. AI4PublicPolicy Conceptual Model

2.1 CRISP-DM Methodology

In 2000, as response to common issues and needs, an industry-driven methodology called Cross-Industry Standard Process for Data Mining (CRISP-DM) was introduced as an alternative to

Knowledge Discovery in Databases (KDD), a previous data mining methodology [CRISP-DM]. It also consolidated the original KDD model and its various extensions. The iterative executions of CRISP-DM stand as the most distinguishing feature compared to initial KDD that assumes a sequential execution of its steps. CRISP-DM, much like KDD, aims at providing practitioners with guidelines to perform data mining on large datasets.

The main steps of CRISP-DM, as depicted in Figure 3 below are as follows:

Figure 3. CRISP-DM Methodology

- **Phase 1 - Business understanding:** The focus of the first step is to gain an understanding of the project objectives and requirements from a business perspective followed by converting these into data mining problem definitions. Presentation of a preliminary plan to achieve the objectives are also included in this first step.
- **Phase 2 - Data understanding:** This step begins with an initial data collection and proceeds with activities in order to get familiar with the data, identify data quality issues, discover first insights into the data, and potentially detect and form hypotheses.
- **Phase 3 - Data preparation:** The third step covers activities required to construct the final dataset from the initial raw data. Data preparation tasks are performed repeatedly.
- **Phase 4 - Modelling phase:** In this step, various modelling techniques are selected and applied followed by calibrating their parameters. Typically, several techniques are used for the same data mining problem.
- **Phase 5 - Evaluation of the model(s):** The fifth step begins with the quality perspective and then, before proceeding to final model deployment, ascertains that the model(s) achieves the business objectives. At the end of this phase, a decision should be reached on how to use data mining results.
- **Phase 6 - Deployment:** In the final step, the models are deployed to enable end-customers to use the data as basis for decisions, or support in the business process. Even if the purpose of the model is to increase knowledge of the data, the knowledge gained will need to be organized, presented, and distributed in a way that the end-user can use it. Depending on the requirements, the deployment phase can be as simple as generating a report or as complex as implementing a repeatable data mining process.

2.2 AI-based Policy Making Process

The AI4PublicPolicy Policy Making Process leverages on the CRISP-DM methodology to address the following objectives:

- Provide a data-driven, AI-based and evidence-based approach
- Promote and facilitate the collaboration between Policy Makers and AI Experts
- Involve citizens and other stakeholders in the Policy evaluation and optimization
- Boost the acceptance of the policies presenting and explaining the Policy development outcomes
- Reuse and share the Policy development models and Datasets

Figure 4. AI4PublicPolicy Policy making Process

The main steps of the Policy Making Process, as depicted in Figure 4 above are as follows:

- **Phase 1 - Policy Definition:** In this step the Policy Maker starts creating an Analytical Policy Model describing the Policy problem(s) and associating and describing relevant Datasets for the Policy.
- **Phase 2 - Policy Extraction:** In this step an AI Expert, or the Policy Maker himself with AutoML support, creates one or more AI Workflows to analyse the datasets and prepare the data to train and test AI Models based on different AI Algorithms, in order to provide responses (insight, recommendations) to the Policy problem(s). The Policy Maker executes the AI Models on new data, analyses the responses and validates the AI Models.
- **Phase 3 - Policy Evaluation:** In this step the Policy Maker involves the relevant stakeholders (citizens, business and other local actors). in the Policy Evaluation creating one or more surveys on the Policy problems, AI model responses and Policy alternatives. The Policy Maker then evaluates stakeholders' feedback, presented with a statistical or sentiment scoring, and decides to complete the Policy with actionable outcomes or optimizing it taking into account stakeholder's feedback.
- **Phase 4 - Policy Presentation and Sharing:** In this step the Policy Maker uses XAI techniques provided by the platform to better understand and explain the rationale behind

the AI Models responses. Once completed this step the Policy Maker could present the final Analytical Policy Model, which represent the result of the AI-based Policy Making Process, to the relevant stakeholders and publish it in the shared catalogue.

2.3 Policy Lifecycle

Along with the AI-based Policy making process described in the previous paragraph, a Policy object assumes different states. The Figure 5 below describes the whole Policy lifecycle.

Figure 5. Policy lifecycle

3 Reference Architecture

3.1 BDV Reference Model

AI4PublicPolicy's main focus is on collecting and analysing data for making public policy. The BDV reference model was defined by the BDVA and it is a framework to locate data related technologies [BDVA]. The reference model is structured into different horizontal and vertical concerns represented in Figure 6. The horizontal concerns represent core components of the data value chain, while horizontal concerns represent cross-cutting issues that may affect all the horizontal concerns. The horizontal concerns, although represented as a stack, are independent layers.

The *data visualization* and user interaction layer deals with the tools for representing big data and the interaction between users and the visualisation of the big data.

Data analytics deals with the techniques for understanding and extracting knowledge from data. These include machine learning, deep learning, natural language processing, event and pattern discovery, deep learning technologies, and high-performance data analytics that take advantage of high-performance computing.

Data processing architectures must deal with data at rest (stored data) and data in motion (streams of data) coming from heterogeneous resources in different formats (structured, non-structured). The data processing architectures must be designed so that they can take advantage of high-performance computing and cloud computing in order to scale to the increasing amount of data being produced.

Figure 6. BDVA Reference Model

Data protection deals with the techniques to protect person-specific and sensitive data. Privacy protection includes protecting analytics applications and the (cloud) underlying infrastructure from data leakages. These mechanisms must ensure anonymity and protection against reversibility.

Data management deals with the techniques for dealing with large amounts of data that are being produced. Multilingualism of data sources, especially relevant in EU, makes it difficult to analyse the data since they are in different languages. The lack of a common representation of the data creates silos of data that cannot be processed without a semantic interoperability layer.

Cloud and High-Performance Computing (HPC) are basic pillars for effective data processing and management. The use of cloud for data processing is a standard nowadays. All cloud platforms provide different infrastructures for storing and analysing data. The use of HPC resources has been recognized as a complementary approach for extreme data analytics. The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is a federated system based on a set of existing research infrastructures which delivers a catalogue of services, software, and data from major research infrastructures.

Among the vertical aspects it is worth mentioning the marketplaces for sharing data and facilitating the usage of horizontal aspects.

3.2 Relation between BDV Reference Model and AI4PublicPolicy

AI4PublicPolicy aims at delivering an Open Virtualized Policy Management Environment for automated, transparent and citizen centric development of public policies. For that purpose, AI4PublicPolicy will collect, process and analyse large volumes of datasets from different data sources (e.g., citizens, public authorities' databases, social media, etc.) using AI technologies and cloud computing resources. AI4PublicPolicy will integrate technologies for semantic interoperability of different data policy data sources, leveraging existing ontologies for policy description. AI4PublicPolicy will be integrated with EOSC that will ensure that public authorities have access to cloud and HPC resources.

More specifically, AI4PublicPolicy addresses the following concerns of the BDV Reference Model:

- *Data Analytics.* AI4PublicPolicy will use AI tools for policy modelling, extraction, simulation and recommendation. The AI tools to be used in AI4PublicPolicy include machine learning to extract policy related knowledge from large datasets, opinion mining and sentiment analysis based on the opinions of citizens expressed in social media.
- *Data Protection.* AI4PublicPolicy will use anonymized data.
- *Data Processing Architectures.* AI4PublicPolicy will deal with data-at-rest or stored data coming from policy authorities and the interaction of citizens with the administration and the services they provide. The AI4PublicPolicy architecture will also deal with streaming data coming from citizens' opinions on social media. So the architecture must integrate both kinds of data management and analytics tools.
- *Data management.* AI4PublicPolicy will deal with structured data (data in tables) and unstructured data (opinions in natural language). AI4PublicPolicy will use natural language processing tools for avoiding the creation of policy data silos in different languages. AI4PublicPolicy development is guided by five pilots from different European countries with different languages. The project will integrate tools for semantic interoperability of policy data sources.
- *Cloud and High-Performance Computing.* AI4PublicPolicy will be integrated with the EOSC portal to facilitate access to cloud and HPC resources.
- *Data sharing platforms.* AI4PublicPolicy integration with EOSC portal will deliver a complete environment for AI-based policy making which will enable sharing datasets, policies and the AI4PublicPolicy VPME.
- *Cybersecurity and Trust.* AI4PublicPolicy will provide *eXplainable AI* (XAI) which will allow to make explicit the rationale behind the policy recommendations and which data were driving the decisions. AI4PublicPolicy will deliver defence strategies against poisoning attacks of data that may have an impact on the learned models.

3.3 AI4PublicPolicy Components

The definition of the software architecture is derived from the requirements of the use cases defined by the pilots in deliverable D2.1 Use Case Scenarios Definition and Design and the feedback received from the pilots after the initial versions of the components were released. Figure 7 presents the main components of AI4PublicPolicy. These components are logically grouped into three main modules that represent three technical work packages of the project according to the DoA that is, Reusable and Interoperable Policies (WP3), Transparent and Trusted AI for Policy Management (WP4) and AI Tools for Autonomous Policy Making (WP5). All these components are independent

components that provide REST interfaces. The architecture notation is derived from the UML notation using lollipop notation for the interfaces. The *half circle* indicates the user of an interface provided by the *ball*.

The target users of the AI4PublicPolicy platform are policy makers and data scientists. The entry point of AI4PublicPolicy for both types of users is the VPME, which is a web application that acts as the user interface (UI) and acts as front-end for all the functionalities of the AI4PublicPolicy platform. Depending on the type of user (policy maker, data scientist), the VPME will present different functionality; for instance, the data scientist may define analytical workflows while the policy maker which is not aware of the different ML techniques may use AutoML features.

There are external data sources such as social media (e.g., Twitter interface) or other forums from which data for opinion mining and sentiment analysis is collected.

Figure 7. AI4PublicPolicy Architecture Components

The sections that follow provide a detailed description of each part of the architecture of AI4PublicPolicy. Each component’s functionality is described detailing the subcomponents, its inputs and outputs.

3.3.1 Policy and Datasets Management

Component Description

The goal of this component is to provide the software tools needed to collect and manage the datasets that will produce the pilots in the project and also to define and manage policies. This tool should be generic enough so that it can be used for collecting other datasets and policies. The datasets will be stored to be later analysed or make them available for others in case of data that can be made public. The software should be generic enough so that it can be used with different datasets and data formats. Another requirement of the component is that it should be able to collect data-at-rest (e.g., from CSV files) or data-at-movement (e.g., streaming data from sensors).

The collection of datasets is done through a web service (REST API) that datasets providers will connect to for providing information on the location of the dataset to be loaded into AI4PublicPolicy platform. Figure 8 shows the subcomponents of the Policy and Data Management component. The Web Interface allows users to interact with the Policy and Data Management component through a web page. The Dataset Management subcomponent also provides a REST API and allows the definition and management of datasets schemas and to upload and download dataset files stored in

EGI DataHub¹, a remote file system based on OneData². Dataset schemas are stored in a database. The Policy Management subcomponent also provides a REST API for the definition and management of policies and AI Models. Both the policies and AI models' definitions are stored in the same database used by the Dataset Management subcomponent.

Figure 8. Policy and Data Management subcomponents

Input

Data set format, endpoint for the input dataset, datastore endpoint.

Output

Data, Policy or AI model in a AI4PublicPolicy datastore.

Dataset Management REST API

The Dataset Management subcomponent provides a REST API that can be used by external users and is used by other AI4PublicPolicy components to interact with it. It provides several operations to create, read, update and delete (CRUD) dataset schemas, list all the dataset files stored for a particular dataset schema in EGI DataHub and upload/download dataset files for a particular dataset schema to EGI DataHub. Figure 9 shows the Swagger definition of the Dataset Management REST API.

¹ <https://datahub.eqi.eu/ozw/onezone/i#/login>

² <https://onedata.org/#/home>

Figure 9. Dataset Management component REST API

Policy Management REST API

Figure 10 shows the Swagger definition of all operations provided by the Policy Management component REST API.

Figure 10. Policy Management component REST API

The implementation of this component as well as the usage of the Policy and Data Management component is detailed in deliverable D3.2 - Data Management and APIs for Data Collection v2.

3.3.2 Semantic Interoperability

Component Description

The goal of the Semantic Interoperability toolkit is to dynamically enable interoperability. It aids datasets on becoming interoperable without the user changes, by acting as an interoperability mediator. Realising interoperability is a key challenge due to the existence of multiple ontologies and archetypes for policy making [Xue22], that need to semantically interoperate.

The semantic interoperability toolkit will be based on the Plug'n'Interoperate solution [Malo13], by exploiting the same basic principle of Plug'n'Play / self-configuration as to automate as much as possible, the configuration and participation of systems into the Interoperability environment. The solution is made possible by the existence of 'interoperability drivers' which define translations in between data formats, and that are taken by an interoperability support system to enable fully interoperability of systems in the data exchange environment. In the Plug'n'Interoperate environment, systems simply plug (into the interoperability support system) and promptly interoperate with other systems present in the data-sharing environment.

Like Pnl, the semantic interoperability toolkit will provide interoperability enabling methods, in order to ensure interoperability between Public Policy datasets. The interoperability toolkit allows datasets from different pilots to be made interoperable in a seamless manner, allowing the definition of semantic queries that collect data from the different datasets regardless of the data formats and semantic model used to describe them.

To achieve this goal, the semantic interoperability toolkit will rely on a GraphQL-based technologic solution to support the definition of queries, describing the information and any relevant restrictions that may restrict the collection of information using the GraphQL query language. Each Public Policy dataset will require its own *Schema* describing the dataset in a GraphQL aligned schema. Each one of the schemas needs to be paired with a *Resolver* component that will be in charge of mapping concepts of the Policies Datasets to the concepts described on the schemas, supporting the execution of the queries over the datasets. With this approach, the addition of each new Public Policy dataset to the interoperable environment will require the provisioning of the corresponding pair of Schema-Resolver.

The schemas with the description of each Public Policy dataset must be provided to the Semantic Interoperability toolkit engine in order for their data to be reachable by the semantic queries. When linked to the Semantic Interoperability toolkit, a supergraph will be generated that will be used to guide the engine on solving the query parameters by routing the engine the schemas (and resolvers) that will provide the required data.

The result from the queries, as usual in GraphQL queries, will be presented in a JSON format respecting the structure defined in the GraphQL query. However, this JSON must also provide information about the semantic concepts associated with it to keep the semantic context of the information. This is achieved by presenting the results in a JSON-LD format, where each data field is associated with the URI to the concept that describes it.

Users of the Semantic Interoperability toolkit may require receiving the results formatted according to a specific data format and semantic model. To support this, the Semantic Interoperability tool will support the integration with different *Semantic Exporters* that will support the export from JSON-LD to the desired models.

Input

As inputs the Semantic Interoperability toolkit will support two types of inputs: user inputs and system inputs.

User inputs correspond to inputs given by users to operate the semantic toolkit. Those inputs correspond to:

- Semantic query description.
- Identification of the desired target semantic model.

System inputs correspond to the inputs and configuration needed for the semantic toolkit to operate. This corresponds to:

- Schemas, and resolvers used onboard Public Policies onto the Semantic Interoperability toolkit engine.
- Exporters required to convert the JSON-LD with the query results into target data model.

Output

As output the Semantic Interoperability toolkit provides the results from the semantic queries, either in a JSON-LD format or other format specified for the output.

Architecture

Figure 11 presents the overall architecture of the Semantic Interoperability Toolkit, representing the elements that are required to connect the Public Policy Datasets to the toolkit - Dataset Integration, that each dataset schema is combined to create a global Schema used to support the description of the queries in the Semantic Interoperability Engine, and how the query results can make use of Exporters to adapt the output to the desired data model. Both the Dataset Integration components and the Exporter in Output Adaption can be added to the Semantic Interoperability Toolkit to enhance its semantic capabilities.

Figure 11. Semantics Interoperability interaction with other components

3.3.3 Cross Country Interoperability

Component Description

This component translates data from the datasets and policies from one language to another target language in order to increase the sharing of data and policies across Europe. Datasets and policies originate in different countries and most of the time are defined in the language of the origin country; this diminishes the chances of data and policies being reused, compared or applied in different countries. This component receives a policy or dataset identifier and the target language and produces the same information in the destination language. This component is implemented using available translation services such as Google translate, which can be integrated with spreadsheets for translating data in tabular form. The architecture of the component is shown in Figure 12. Policy definitions are stored in the database (DB in Figure 12) when a translation request is received the *policy and dataset translator* sub-component retrieves the policy definition from the database, translates it into the target language and stores the translated one in the database. A similar procedure is executed when a dataset translation request is received. The *policy and dataset translator* sub-component gets the location of the dataset file within the EGI DataHub, fetches the original dataset file and translates it producing a new dataset file in the target language.

Figure 12. Cross Country Interoperability component architecture

Input

Text to be translated, target language.

Output

Text in the target language.

REST API

The Cross Country Interoperability component provides a REST API that can be used by users and other components to request the translation of a particular policy or dataset. Two operations are provided, one for the translation of datasets and another one for the translation of a policy. Figure 13 shows the REST API Swagger interface.

Figure 13. Cross Country Interoperability Swagger REST API

3.3.4 Datasets and Policies Catalogue

Component Description

The Catalogue for Policies & Datasets is a component which will list all Policies and Datasets related to AI4PublicPolicies. All information interesting for the execution of the project will be hosted in a searchable catalogue, which can be of use for users that need information related to policies and datasets for specific situations.

Apart from the increased searchability, the catalogue will provide more knowledge base functionalities for comparison and recommendation of datasets and/or policies. By modelling datasets and policies, along with associated metadata, the catalogue can offer some decision

support system functionalities, such as recommendation of related datasets or policies. This can be accomplished using a “similarity rank”, and when a user accesses a specific entry in the catalogue, it will also receive information about related datasets and/or policies.

Input

This component needs as input information about the dataset or policy that should be listed, and then it will retrieve and show the information about the specific dataset and the related datasets.

Output

This data is stored on the Catalogue and could be accessed by a user through a web interface or by an external application using a rest API, both access methods provide authentication for private data access.

- *Web Interfaces:* they allow the interaction through several web pages containing data available on the catalogue, a username/ password could be required when accessing restricted information.
- *REST APIs:* Used to enable the communication between the catalogue and external services, a token could be required when accessing restricted information.

Catalogue Rest API 1.0.0 OAS3

Used to enable the communication between the catalogue and external services, a token could be required when accessing restricted information. The Rest API uses JSON for the communication between an external service and the catalogue, providing the following features:

- **Token authentication:** For private accesses an authorized user could be authenticated using an unique token, the token could be revoked to remove the user permission.
- **Data fetching:** Allows an external application to fetch private (when provided a token) and public data.
- **Data Search:** Returns search results based on a query, some wild card like "*" could be used.
- **Data update:** Used to update data available on IoT Catalogue, this feature could be useful in scenarios where the data must be updated on a regular basis, a token is required to use this feature.
- **Adding new data:** Used to insert new data on Catalogue, useful when adding large sets of data, a token is required to use this feature.

[Terms of service](#)

[Contact the developer](#)

Authorize

Catalogue API Get, search, add, edit and remove data from IoT Catalogue

[Find out more](#)

GET	<code>/getData/{elementId}</code> Returns a data element	▼
GET	<code>/getDataList/{elementId}</code> Get a list of data elements	▼
POST	<code>/editDataElement</code> Edit an existing data element	▼
POST	<code>/addNewData</code> Add a new data element	▼
GET	<code>/searchData</code> Returns a list of data elements based on a search queryo Input	▼
DELETE	<code>/deleteDataElement/{elementId}</code> Delete a data element	▼

Figure 14. Datasets Catalogue Swagger REST API

Subcomponents

Figure 15 shows the interaction of the Catalogue using the previously defined subcomponents.

Figure 15. Policies and Datasets Catalogue

3.3.5 XAI Techniques

Component Description

This component is in charge of providing dashboards for analysing and explaining the predictions made by machine learning models. The XAI component gets a model (classifier, regression or decision trees) and a dataset and generates a dashboard for checking the model performance and SHAP values, which rely on input perturbations to explain the model output. Dashboards present a set of interactive aspects the user can control. Examples of plots to be shown are model performance, SHAP dependence plot, impact of a feature on a predicted value, SHAP interaction, features importance. A set of default dashboards for each pilot will be developed. This component is implemented using Dalex Arena³, which can be integrated with Jupyter notebooks that will be used for building the models in AI4PublicPolicy VPME. An example dashboard is shown in Figure 16. A synthetic dataset with the features of different apartments has been loaded and a set of models has been trained with the dataset. The dashboard allows the user to select the model to be analysed from the menu bar on the right side of the dashboard, in this case the Gradient boosting (gbm) model is selected. Then, a set of plots are produced for that model and can be added into the dashboard, in this case three charts are added into the dashboard: the Metrics, Funnel Plot and Error charts.

³ <https://arena.drwhy.ai/docs/>

Figure 16. XAI Dashboard example

Figure 17 shows the internal architecture of the XAI component, which is made of two subcomponents, the REST API and the XAI Dashboard. The REST API is used to interact with the XAI Dashboard. The XAI Dashboard visualises different charts for explaining the decisions made by the models.

Figure 17. XAI Techniques internal architecture

Input

The predefined dashboards receive the type of model (classifier, regression, decision tree), a model and a dataset.

Output

The XAI component produces an interactive dashboard integrated with Jupyter notebooks.

REST API

The XAI component provides a REST API to add new models and datasets to the XAI Technique dashboards dynamically. Figure 18 shows the REST API Swagger interface.

XAI Techniques
 This is the first version of the XAI Techniques component REST API
[Contact the developer](#)

Model : All operations to add new models Show/Hide List Operations Expand Operations

- POST** /model Add a new model to the XAI Dashboard
- DELETE** /model/{modelId} Deletes a Model
- GET** /model/{modelId} Find model by ID
- POST** /model/{modelId} Updates a model in the XAI DASHBOARD with form data

Dataset : All operations to add new datasets Show/Hide List Operations Expand Operations

- POST** /dataset Add a new dataset to the XAI Dashboard
- DELETE** /dataset/{datasetId} Deletes a dataset
- GET** /dataset/{datasetId} Find dataset by ID
- POST** /dataset/{datasetId} Updates a dataset in the XAI DASHBOARD with form data

[BASE URL: /xai-techniques , API VERSION: 1.0.0]

Figure 18. XAI Techniques Swagger REST API

Sequence Diagram

Figure 19 shows the EXplainable AI flow.

Figure 19. EXplainable AI Techniques interaction with other components

3.3.6 Policy Explainability and Interpretation

Component Description

This component will realise the tools to build the policy models which will produce the analysis and interpretation of the policy datasets given by the project's pilots (Athens, Lisbon, Nicosia, Genova and Burgas). The policy models will produce insights drawn from the datasets and forecasts on each unique scenario presented below. The policy maker will be able to understand the patterns existing in data and the models forecasts in order to fine-tune or shape future policies.

- **Athens Pilot:**

- Maintenance Policies Optimization.
 - Optimal allocation of maintenance resources based:
 - On prediction of types of issues that may arise for certain authorities of the municipality.
 - Prediction of the number of issues that may arise for certain authorities of the municipality.
 - Predictive citizen-centric of parking policies development.
 - Visualisations to help understand the “hidden information” in the dataset.
 - Forecasts for the available parking spaces in a near future window for each parking zone available in the dataset.

- **Genova Pilot:**

- Implementation of a tool which will allow policy makers:
 - Identify the set of decision variables for the policy maker to see how their use can reduce the risk of accident against vulnerable subjects.
 - Run what-if scenarios to understand how the risk of accident could change based on relevant features and decision variables

- **Lisbon Pilot:**

- Combination of the data given in order to create a sustainability index.
 - The sustainability index will be implemented based on generally known sustainability targets/standards.
- The results can be either given in a textual format or can be visualised in a map depicting the city's regions.

- **Burgas Pilot:**

- Implementation of a tool which will be able to detect leakages in the water pipes of Burgas. It will enable the municipality of Burgas to fix or replace the defective pipes before the damage will result in huge water losses.

- **Nicosia Pilot:**

- Analysis of bus routes & occupancy, parking usage and citizens preferences in order to propose the best alternative for the citizen in relation to travel time and travel costs.

- Analyse bus routes, parking spaces revenues and environmental performance (CO2 emissions, fuel consumption) in order to improve environmental performance and management for the city.
- Produce inclusiveness zones for disabled people based on the bus routes and environmental performance (CO2 emissions, fuel consumption) datasets.

The different scenarios described for each pilot are created upon the inspection of available datasets. A transformation can take place to them after the finalisation of the use cases from the provided user stories.

Among the technologies which will be used for the implementation of the tools will be Machine Learning and Deep Learning algorithms (e.g., clustering algorithms, QARMA (INTRASOFT's ML algorithm), Artificial Neural Networks etc.) through Keras and Tensorflow libraries. The optimization technologies which will probably be used are widely known solvers such as Gurobi, SCIP and OR-Tools.

Input

Datasets which are described in deliverables D1.10 and D2.3.

Output

The component will have as output the policy models build upon the input datasets. These models will perform analysis on the data and will produce a variety of visualisations and in addition forecasts that can be used by the policy maker in order to reshape or create a variety of policies. Indicative examples of policies that can be drawn from each scenario are:

- **Athens Pilot**

Based on the forecasts for the available parking spaces a policy can be made in order to raise or lessen the parking prices so as to increase the municipality's profit or to enhance the parking space availability.

- **Genova Pilot**

Based on the forecasts for the risk of an accident in a street under certain conditions, a policy can be made (reduce speed limit, change numbers of way, add crosswalks or traffic lights, ...) to reduce the risk.

- **Lisbon Pilot**

Through creating and visualising a sustainability index a policy maker will be able to have a clear view of the city's areas index and maybe he will be able to produce policies in order to enhance the sustainability index of areas that have small index scores.

- **Burgas Pilot**

The policy model will use vibration and other data to detect whether a pipe may have a leakage or not and will also try to pinpoint its location. The model will then estimate the optimal schedule of maintenance and replacement by minimizing costs and disruption from excavation works.

- **Nicosia Pilot**

Through the analysis of the bus routes, parking spaces revenues and occupancy and the environmental performance it will be possible to build visualisations which will help explain hidden insights from the data and build ML models and optimization algorithms

that will be able to predict/output the best way to travel from a point A to B, the most environment friendly one and cost effective. Furthermore, it will be attempted to develop better city services for the disabled people and enhance their quality of life.

REST API

The Policy Interpretation module has and will also enhance a REST API which lets other developers within the project and the other interconnected modules to use the models developed for this module. The functions so far support to post or delete models, post new datasets to be used for prediction and furthermore to use the existing already built models.

Figure 20. Policy Interpretation REST API Swagger

3.3.7 AI Security

Component Description

The objective of this component is to deliver defence strategies against AI threats that will attempt to sabotage AI models in ways that compromise their correct operation. In particular, the mechanisms should primarily protect the AI systems against data poisoning and evasion attacks. Starting with the data poisoning attacks, in the data collected from our data sources, an attacker can potentially inject designated adversarial samples into training data to affect the resulting decision function. Hence, ensuring the purity of training data and improving the robustness of learning algorithms are two main countermeasures towards such adversaries at the training phase.

In this case the Cyber-Defence tool must check the data received from the various data sources and possibly detect any anomalies in the samples. Here different strategies are available as a detection based on data provenance strategy and the XAI techniques.

To protect against evasion attacks the defence tool will train the model using new inputs with adversarial perturbations and correct output labels aiming at minimising the errors caused by adversarial data. The adversarial inputs can be taken from the output of the previous poisoning defence phase or using automatic adversarial techniques.

In particular we are considering a revisited adversarial training technique, which trains empirically robust models using Fast Gradient Sign method for the adversarial training and has significantly lower cost respect to the projected gradient descent-based training. Figure 21 below shows a high-level architecture of the defensive process.

Figure 21. AI Security defensive process architecture

Input

Poisoning Detector:

- data collected from the pilot sources

Evasion Training:

- policy model

Output

Poisoning Detector:

- sanitized training data

Evasion Training:

- robust policy model

3.3.8 AutoML

Component Description

This is a component for selecting among a set of well-established algorithms the optimal algorithm to realise the AI processes chain. The mechanism realising the latter will automatically extract statistical meta-features from datasets to perform an optimum mapping, while also considering all processes steps and dependencies within an analysis pipeline / chain. These are following subcomponents:

Dataset Explorer

1. User selects the datasets that will serve as an input to the AutoML tool.
2. Selects parameters of the data loading:
 - Columns to load/ignore.
 - Target column (the value of which should be predicted).

- Some transformation of the data (like featurization of dateTime values to separate fields (day, weekday, month)).
3. Source of the data: DB or raw CSV file.

Data Visualizer

After the data set is selected the user can preview the data in the

- Table preview
- Maybe some other graphical representation of the data

AutoML Pipeline

A subcomponent which allows the user to choose parameters of the AutoML Engine (defaults are used if nothing is selected) and start the AutoML process.

Parameters to select (specific to the AutoML engine used):

- Search algorithm
- General timeout
- Iteration timeout
- Algorithms filter
- Early stopping (conditions)
- Number of cross validations

AutoML Engine

A component that takes datasets, parameters from the user as an input and finds the best models that fit.

Input

- Dataset
- Policy

Output

Policy Model with the following additional details:

- Algorithm name
- Metaparameters of the model
- Accuracy
- Datasets used for training the model
- Feature importance: features are ranked based on their influence on the trained model

Extraction flow

The subcomponents and the pipeline for the AutoML component are shown in Figure 22.

Figure 22. AutoML internal architecture

3.3.9 Sentiment Analysis

Component Description

The purpose of the Sentiment Analysis component is to provide the sentiment of citizens' feedback to policy makers, exploiting data from conversations, declarations or even tweets. In order to process

the extensive content collected from pilots' different data sources, the sentiment of each sentence/body is evaluated using complex Machine Learning models, as well as robust and load-balanced data processing pipelines.

Sentiment analysis models specialize in polarity (positive, negative, neutral) but, also in emotions (angry, happy, sad, etc.). The input data is in raw text format, the data then is processed using the NLP pipeline for text classification that we have developed. The task aims to the improvement of evidence-based policy making, leveraging the huge amount of user-generated content that exists in multiple external sources, to support the formulation of public policies.

For the sentiment analysis component, a REST API has been developed to provide the sentiment and emotion analysis of text extracted from either Twitter or comments. This component is a service and it does not require any further resources from the client-side.

REST API

The API design conforms to the constraints of the REST architectural style and provides a great deal of flexibility for the user. All requests are POST requests and return the result as JSON output. Since the API is publicly available, an X-API-KEY header (secret) is being used as an authentication technique, to authenticate incoming requests and avoid usage from unauthorized users.

An outline of the architecture is displayed in Figure 23. The architecture of the API aims to be very easy to interact with since all endpoints just require a "text" argument to be completed in the body of the request. The pre-processing of the text is achieved with tokenization, which converts text input into numbers that the model can understand. Providing the text, the API recognizes the language and redirects the appropriate model under the hood, without additional input from the user's side. After the model evaluation, the output post-processing decodes the result into distinct human-readable classes and returns it in JSON format.

Figure 23. Architecture Outline

Input

Raw text from different pilots' sources e.g., citizens' tweets, comments from various platforms, complaints, reports, or surveys.

Output

The result of the API is in JSON format, where it contains the:

- Identified language
- Predicted class of the emotion or sentiment analysis
- Associated probability score of the prediction
- Initial text

The available API endpoints have been split by the type of source (comments or Twitter), by language and by task, which in this case is the sentiment and emotion classifications. The token will be provided by RBP until the integration into VPME where the token generation will be available throughout the platform.

Comments analytics focuses on opinions posted by users about a particular entity. The available languages for both sentiment and emotion analysis are English (en), Greek (el), Italian (it), Portuguese(pt), and Bulgarian (bg). The available endpoints (Figure 24) and classes of each model can be found below:

Endpoint: `/sentiment/comments`

- Labels: positive, negative, neutral

Endpoint: `/emotion/comments`

- Labels: anger, disgust, joy, neutral, sadness, surprise

comments		^
POST	<code>/sentiment/comments</code> Post Comments Sentiment	v 🔒
POST	<code>/emotion/comments</code> Post Comments Emotion	v 🔒

Figure 24. REST API for Comments

Text from tweets is usually noisy, so we are pre-processing and cleaning the input text to remove symbols such as (@, #, etc). Tweets are usually very different from other forms of comments or text on social media, because they are restricted to 280 characters and tend to be more opinionated than other forms. Supported languages are English(en), Greek (el), Italian (it), Portuguese(pt), Bulgarian (bg). The available endpoints (Figure 25) and classes of each model can be found below:

Endpoint: `/sentiment/twitter`

- Labels: positive, negative, neutral

Endpoint: `/emotion/twitter`

- Labels: love, joy, sadness, surprise, anger, fear

twitter		^
POST	<code>/sentiment/twitter</code> Post Twitter Sentiment	v 🔒
POST	<code>/emotion/twitter</code> Post Twitter Emotion	v 🔒

Figure 25. REST API for Twitter

3.3.10 Text Analysis

Component Description

Text Analysis aims to transform raw (unstructured) text from different sources and databases into normalized, structured data, suitable for analysis. The tools for this component are being developed based on natural language processing (NLP) technologies and machine learning models and they

include tasks such as Named Entity Recognition (NER) for the extraction of persons, organisations or locations from text, as well as keyword extraction. The text analytics will be powered by a REST API, to support the policy evaluation and policy making processes.

REST API

The Text Analysis component is a work in progress. REST API for text analysis will follow the same architecture as for sentiment analysis.

Input

Raw text from different pilots' sources

Output

Text analytics:

- Persons, organisations and locations
- Keywords and key phrases that are the most similar to the text itself

3.3.11 Policy Extraction

Component Description

This component provides a set of tools to the AI expert and policy makers to build an AI pipeline and AI model and apply it to the relevant dataset in order to extract the best policy according to predefined KPIs. The component provides the functionality to browse the catalogue of policies, pipelines, and policy models. An AI expert and policy maker can compare different models and choose the best one for the policy and KPI.

Figure 26 shows the sub-components of the policy extraction toolkit.

Figure 26. Policy extraction toolkit subcomponents

Subcomponents

Open Analytical Environment

An environment in which an AI expert can design an AI experiment and run it. In our implementation we use JupyterHub which serves Jupyter notebooks that are used to design AI experiments, create AI pipelines and train models.

Pipeline Manager

Responsible for tracking all the runs of the experiments and their parameters, metrics and artefacts (i.e., AI models, graphs, KPIs); MLFlow is utilised for this purpose.

Model Manager

Responsible for tracking and comparing models, managing their status, making them available to other components; MLFlow is utilised for this purpose.

User Interface

Web UI that allows an AI expert and a policy maker to perform all necessary actions during the whole lifecycle of the policy extraction process.

Code Repository

Storing AI projects, project templates and other artefacts.

Input

- Policy
- Datasets

Output

- Policy AI model
- Model metadata (algorithm, parameters, accuracy, features importance)
- AI pipelines (for training and inference phases)

REST API

The Policy Extraction component provides a REST API that can be used by the VPME web application and by other AI4PublicPolicy components. It provides operations for managing AI projects, models and pipelines.

Figure 27 shows a REST API definition in Swagger for the functionality related to models:

Figure 27. Policy extraction component REST API (model)

Figure 28 shows a REST API definition for the functionality related to pipelines:

pipeline		Access to Pipelines	Find out more about our store
POST	/pipeline/run/{pipelineId}	Run pipeline	
POST	/pipeline	Create pipeline	
GET	/pipeline/{pipelineId}	Get pipeline	
PUT	/pipeline/{pipelineId}	Update pipeline	
DELETE	/pipeline/{pipelineId}	Delete pipeline	
GET	/pipeline/{pipelineId}/runs	Get pipeline runs	
GET	/pipeline/run/{runId}	Get single execution of the pipeline	
GET	/pipeline/findByStatus	Finds pipelines by status	

Figure 28. Policy extraction component REST API (pipeline)

Figure 29 shows a REST API definition for the functionality related to AI projects:

project		AI Project	Find out more about our store
POST	/project	Create AI project	
GET	/project/{projectId}	Get project by id	
DELETE	/project/{projectId}	Delete project	
GET	/project/policy/{policyId}	Get list of projects for a specified policy	
GET	/project/policy/{policyId}/kpi/{kpi}	Get a project for a specified policy and KPI	

Figure 29. Policy extraction component REST API (project)

3.3.12 Policy Evaluation and Optimization

Component Description

The objective of this component is to allow the simulation and evaluation of the policies developed by making use of the opinions and feedback of local actors to propose new insights and improvements.

In particular, a new virtual environment process will be designed which: in a first phase proposes the developed policy models to local actors and through different channels (existing Pilot applications, online surveys, social media) collects the explicit and implicit feedback using the tools we provide,

and in the subsequent phase these feedbacks are used as inputs to a mechanism that extracts new insights and capabilities to augment the artificial intelligence algorithms. More specifically, the tool for analysing responses can give through graphs and tables an aggregate view of citizens' opinions on a specific policy and help the policy maker make decisions.

The tools that extract feedback from the different channels will adopt mechanisms developed for Sentiment Analysis, Opinion Mining and Text Analytics.

Using the presented procedure, we involve citizens in the policy co-creation process, while allowing the selection of the most correct data sources and policy models considering the expectations of local actors.

Figure 30. Policy evaluation and optimization flow

Input

Policy models as outcome of the AI algorithms and feedback collected from the local actors through different channels

Output

Analytics on the results of citizens' surveys on policy alternatives being evaluated by the Policy Maker

Interface

This Policy Evaluation and Optimization component provides a microservice with a web interface that can be used by Policy Maker and Citizens. Below are the functions present in the exposed interface.

Table 1. Policy Evaluation and Optimization microservice functions

Function	Interface	Description
Manage AI4PP survey	In-App survey generator	Create survey and store it in the local database using the generator tool available

	Create Social survey	Create, publish and manage survey on social channels
	Survey management	Edit, delete and check the status of the surveys available
Feedback analytics	Analytics dashboard interface	Evaluate survey results and analyse feedback responses
Compile survey	In-App survey compiler	Interface for citizens to compile In-App survey available

3.3.13 VPME

Component Description

The VPME will incorporate the policy models, the explainability AI mechanisms outcomes from Explainable AI (XAI) for Policy Interpretation and the Policy Explainability and Interpretation Tools, the Sentiment Analysis and Opinion Mining and Text Analytics for Document Processing components which will create the sentiment analysis, the opinion mining and the text analytics tools respectively and finally the security interfaces. The aforementioned technology components which will be incorporated in the VPME platform will be accessed through their APIs. The VPME will be a cloud-based platform and will be realised through Jupyter Notebooks from which all the different components will be connected through the API each component will offer. Each Pilot will have a set of Jupyter Notebooks which will analyse each dataset and then the proper visualisations will be produced along with the model’s forecasts. The above VPME description is also depicted in the Sequence Diagram section.

Input

Models and functionalities for AI-based reusable and interoperable policies, explainable AI (XAI) for policy interpretation, policy explainability and interpretation tools, secure operation of AI algorithms and tools, AutoML for public administrators, sentiment analysis and Opinion Mining and Text Analytics for Document Processing along with the Policy-Related Datasets.

Output

A Cloud based platform based on a set of Jupyter Notebooks through which the user will be able to control the models and functionalities created by the different set of tools.

Subcomponents

Figure 31. VPME subcomponents

VPME User Interface (UI)

VPME platform is a combination of modules which will be interconnected between them. All the relevant modules will have a common user interface (UI). A first draft UI of the main VPME platform page has been developed in order to gather comments on its look and feel and continue to the second version. It will act as the main interface which will be responsible to direct the users to all its major components.

Figure 32. VPME main interface initial UI

3.4 AI4PublicPolicy Infrastructure

The AI4PublicPolicy services will be built on top of the multi-layered EOSC Compute Platform shown in Figure 33. Its main layers are:

- The *Federated Resource Providers* layer provides an Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS) hybrid infrastructure from academic and commercial providers to run and/or host research applications and data. Its components are provided by cloud providers and HPC centres from different European countries.

- The *Compute and Data Federation* layer provides advanced solutions for facilitating common and recurring tasks such as data management and transfer, virtual infrastructure orchestration and software distribution.
- The *Platforms* layer provides a higher abstraction layer on top of the previous one, offering generic Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS) services such as interactive notebook environment, machine learning and deep learning applications for data analysis, scalable big data tools, and workload management tools.
- The vertical *Service Management Tools* layer includes Helpdesk, Monitoring, Accounting, Operations Management, Security and Incident response, and Software Quality Assurance services.

Figure 33. Infrastructure architecture

The infrastructure will provide technologies to allocate cloud and HPC resources like computing, data storing and sharing to facilitate the management of containers for the execution of the AI models created in the project. These resources will be offered through the European Cloud Initiative. EGI FedCloud services will be used where applicable.

The infrastructure is populated by data, applications, scripts, AI models etc. from project pilots and application developers.

The infrastructure will provide technologies to allocate cloud and HPC resources like computing, data storing and sharing to facilitate the management of containers for the execution of the AI models created in the project. These resources will be offered through the European Cloud Initiative. EGI FedCloud services will be used where applicable.

The infrastructure is populated by data, applications, scripts, AI models etc. from project pilots and application developers.

3.4.1 Service Management Tools

Access to datasets and applications hosted on the Compute Platform can be defined through Check-in, one of the main services provided by the Service Management Tools layer.

Authentication and Authorization: Check-in is the authentication, authorisation and user management service for the EGI infrastructure. It enables users to access EGI, and third-party services (web and non-web based), using existing credentials managed by the Identity Providers (IdPs) of their home organisations. The Check-in service enables users to:

- manage their accounts from a single interface
- link multiple accounts/identities together
- access services based on their roles and Virtual Organisation (VO)/group membership rights

3.4.2 Federated Resource Providers

The Federated Resource Providers layers is the bottom layer of the infrastructure providing computing and data resources both on cloud and HPC.

Cloud providers: Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS) Cloud is provided by research cloud providers from many European countries and is based on OpenStack. It can be accessed through Check-in via web-dashboard, API and command line interface (CLI). They allow provision of low-level storage such as block storage and object storage as well as Virtual Machines (VMs) and Kubernetes cluster among other things.

HPC: High-Performance Computing (HPC) supports highly optimized applications that need massively parallel computing with low latency and high bandwidth interconnection networks such as complex computational problems using tightly coupled parallel processing: simulations, analysis of large datasets or AI workloads. It provides highly optimized computing systems that deliver large amounts of parallel computing power to run such applications and offers a managed service where you can find a fully operational environment where to submit your jobs. In most HPC systems, user access is performed via the Secure Shell Protocol (SSH) to a set of login nodes where users can interact with the system and submit jobs for their execution. In those providers who deliver HPC hardware via IaaS interfaces, an HPC system can be deployed using tools such as Elastic Cloud Compute Cluster.

3.4.3 Compute and Data Federation

The Compute and Data Federation layer provides advanced solutions to manage the resources available in the Federated Resource Providers layer such as the DataHub for the federation and management of data and the cloud orchestrators for the management of the compute resources.

DataHub: EGI DataHub is a federated service, integrated with EGI Check-in allowing users to access and share their data from anywhere using either fully restricted access based on access tokens or publicly shared data sets. EGI DataHub is provisioned based on the Onedata distributed data access and management system. DataHub is a globally distributed storage solution, integrating storage services from various providers using possibly heterogeneous underlying technologies

Figure 34. Federated resource provider layer

DataHub enables seamless sharing of data between users, with strict access control. Users can share access to individual files as well as spaces by sending automatically generated access tokens. All DataHub components have APIs defined using OpenAPI specification version 2.0, enabling easy integration and automatic generation of client libraries for most existing programming languages and frameworks.

Infrastructure Manager: The IM Dashboard is designed to enable non advanced users to launch complex virtual infrastructures on top of a wide range of cloud providers (AWS, Google Cloud, Microsoft Azure, EGI Cloud Computing, OpenNebula, OpenStack, and more ...). Only with a few clicks the user can deploy the set of available topologies expressed through templates written in TOSCA (Simple Profile in YAML version 1.0). Then the IM service orchestrates the whole process: deployment of cloud resources, configuration, software installation, monitoring and update of the virtual infrastructures. Following is a list of functionalities provided by the Infrastructure Manager:

- OIDC authentication
- Display user's infrastructures
- Display infrastructure details, template and log
- Delete infrastructure
- Create new infrastructure
- Add nodes to an infrastructure
- Resize VMs
- Cloud resources

The entry web⁴ page for the tool is shown on the following screenshot:

⁴ <https://www.grycap.upv.es/im/index.php>

Figure 35. Entry web page screenshot

Elastic Cloud Computing Cluster: Elastic Cloud Computing Cluster (EC3) is a tool to create elastic virtual clusters on top of IaaS providers. Being based on Infrastructure Manager (IM) EC3 supports the same wide choices of back-ends. It offers recipes to deploy SLURM, Kubernetes, Apache Mesos and others. EC3 creates elastic cluster-like infrastructures that can automatically scale up or down, depending on demand and the configured policies. This creates the illusion of a real cluster without requiring an investment beyond the actual usage, delivering a cost-effective elastic Cluster-as-a-Service on top of an IaaS cloud.

3.4.4 Platforms layer

The Platforms layer is built on top of the federation, either by using IaaS APIs or Federated IaaS provisioning, and can provide community-specific data, tools and applications. Two relevant services are Notebooks and the DEEP training facility.

Notebook: Jupyter Notebooks complemented with Binder allows users to create data and code-driven narratives made of interactively executable code, equations, descriptive text, interactive dashboards and other rich media. Its integration with the other services of the computing platform, from check-in to DataHub, allows to easily build a community interactive notebook environment, with a fine-grained control on user access, and the possibility to access and share stored data.

4 Validation Matrix

The next table presents the traceability matrix that shows which components are used by each User Story defined for different pilots. This matrix User Stories are defined in deliverable D2.1 Use Case Scenarios Definition and Design.

Table 2. Validation matrix

User Story #	Pilot	V P M E	Policy Evaluation & Optimization	Policy Extraction	Text & Sentiment Analysis	AI Security	Auto ML	Policy Explainability & Interpretation	Semantic Interoperability	Data sets & Policy Catalogue	Cross Country Interoperability	Data set Collection & Management
US01	Athens	•		•			•	•	•			•
US02	Athens	•		•			•		•			•
US03	Athens	•	•					•	•			•
US04	Athens	•			•				•			•
US05	Athens	•		•			•		•			•
US06	Athens	•		•			•		•			•
US07	Athens	•	•						•			•
US08	Athens	•	•						•			•
US09	Athens	•		•			•		•			•
US10	Athens	•		•			•		•			•
US11	Athens	•	•					•	•			•
US12	Athens	•	•			•			•			•
US13	Athens	•	•						•			•
US14	Athens	•	•						•			•
US15	Athens	•	•						•			•
US16	Athens	•		•			•	•	•			•
US17	Athens	•							•			•
US18	Athens	•		•			•		•			•
US19	Athens	•							•			•
US20	Athens	•							•			•

D2.7 Conceptual Model and Reference Architecture V2

User Story #	Pilot	V P M E	Policy Evaluation & Optimization	Policy Extraction	Text & Sentiment Analysis	AI Security	Auto ML	Policy Explainability & Interpretation	Semantic Interoperability	Data sets & Policy Catalogue	Cross Country Interoperability	Data set Collection & Management
US21	Athens	•	•	•			•		•			•
US22	Athens	•				•			•			•
US23	Athens	•	•			•			•			•
US24	Athens	•		•		•	•		•			•
US25	Athens	•		•		•			•			•
US26	Athens	•		•		•	•		•			•
US27	Genoa	•			•	•			•			•
US28	Genoa	•				•			•	•		•
US29	Genoa	•			•	•			•			•
US30	Genoa	•		•		•	•	•	•			•
US31	Genoa	•			•	•		•	•			•
US32	Genoa	•	•	•		•	•	•	•			•
US33	Genoa	•	•	•		•	•		•			•
US34	Genoa	•	•			•			•			•
US35	Genoa	•	•	•		•	•		•			•
US36	Genoa	•				•			•			•
US37	Genoa	•			•	•			•			•
US38	Lisbon	•				•		•	•	•		•
US39	Lisbon	•				•		•	•			•
US40	Lisbon	•	•			•		•	•			•
US41	Lisbon	•			•	•		•	•			•
US42	Lisbon	•		•		•	•	•	•			•
US43	Lisbon	•		•		•	•	•	•			•

D2.7 Conceptual Model and Reference Architecture V2

User Story #	Pilot	V P M E	Policy Evaluation & Optimization	Policy Extraction	Text & Sentiment Analysis	AI Security	Auto ML	Policy Explainability & Interpretation	Semantic Interoperability	Data sets & Policy Catalogue	Cross Country Interoperability	Data set Collection & Management
US44	Lisbon	•				•		•	•			•
US45	Lisbon	•				•		•	•			•
US46	Lisbon	•	•	•		•	•		•			•
US47	Lisbon	•		•		•	•		•			•
US48	Lisbon	•				•		•	•			•
US49	Lisbon	•				•			•		•	•
US50	Lisbon	•				•			•		•	•
US51	Lisbon	•			•	•			•		•	•
US52	Lisbon	•				•			•	•	•	•
US53	Lisbon	•	•			•			•			•
US54	Burgas	•		•		•	•	•	•			•
US55	Burgas	•		•		•	•	•	•			•
US56	Burgas	•				•			•			•
US57	Burgas	•		•		•	•	•	•			•
US58	Burgas	•				•		•	•			•
US59	Burgas	•				•		•	•			•
US60	Burgas	•				•			•			•
US61	Burgas	•				•			•			•
US62	Burgas	•				•		•	•			•
US63	Burgas	•				•			•			•
US64	Burgas	•				•			•			•
US65	Burgas	•				•			•			•
US66	Burgas	•				•			•			•

D2.7 Conceptual Model and Reference Architecture V2

User Story #	Pilot	V P M E	Policy Evaluation & Optimization	Policy Extraction	Text & Sentiment Analysis	AI Security	Auto ML	Policy Explainability & Interpretation	Semantic Interoperability	Data sets & Policy Catalogue	Cross Country Interoperability	Data set Collection & Management
US67	Burgas	•				•			•			•
US68	Burgas	•				•		•	•			•
US69	Burgas	•				•			•			•
US70	Nicosia	•				•			•			•
US71	Nicosia	•		•		•			•			•
US72	Nicosia	•		•		•			•			•
US73	Nicosia	•		•		•			•			•
US74	Nicosia	•		•		•			•			•
US75	Nicosia	•				•			•			•
US76	Nicosia	•				•			•			•

This validation matrix will evolve in the future as the user stories are refined. Future versions of this document will capture the final usage of components by each use case.

5 Scenarios

This section presents a set of scenarios which describes how the end users (Policy Makers, AI Experts, Stakeholders) interact with the components of the AI4PublicPolicy Reference Architecture, described in chapter 3, to implement the main steps of the Policy Making Process as described in chapter 2.

5.1 Registration Process and Login

The login to the VPME is granted through the EGI Check-In service. With it, users can authenticate with their preferred IdP (e.g., an eduGAIN account, institutional account, social media account, etc.). Alternatively, users can create an EGI SSO account and login with this account. Once logged in, users can ask to join a Virtual Organisation (VO), by following a dedicated link, also provided in the enrollment section of the EGI Check-In service.

The request is notified to the VO manager that can accept or deny it. If accepted, it grants users access to the resources available to such VO. The VO manager can subsequently add users to groups of the same VO that might grant additional permissions. The activity diagram in Figure 36 shows the components involved and the sequence of steps just described.

Figure 36. EGI Check-in account registration and VO enrolment diagram

Figure 37 shows the components involved and the steps performed to access the VPME. It will delegate the authentication to the check-in service, and after that it will look for specific attributes associated with each user to grant different levels of access to the platform.

Figure 37. VPME Authentication and Authorization diagram

5.2 New Policy Definition

A policy maker, logged in the VPME, wishes to develop a Policy using an AI-driven approach.

1. The policy maker creates a Policy describing the context and the problem
2. The policy maker adds relevant Datasets to the Policy and describe them
3. The policy maker changes the status of the Policy to “DEFINED”

Figure 38. Policy definition interaction diagram

5.3 Policy Extraction

An AI Expert wishes to create different AI workflows to test different AI Algorithms for a Policy over one or more Policy Datasets.

1. The AI Expert selects a “DEFINED” Policy
2. The AI Expert creates a set of AI Workflow with different AI Algorithms and Tools to address the problem described in the Policy for a specific KPI
3. The AI Expert runs the AI Workflows on one or more Policy Datasets and trains a set of AI Models
4. The AI Expert tests evaluate the performance of the AI Models
5. The AI Expert register the AI Models or updates the AI Workflows and repeat the loop

Figure 39. Policy extraction, create AI workflows interaction diagram

A Policy Maker wishes to receive a policy response for a given policy and the AI model.

1. Policy Maker selects a Policy in “EXTRACTING” state
2. For each KPI the Policy Maker test and compare different AI Models (from that list of available models for that KPI)
3. For each KPI the Policy Maker selects the best model
4. Finally, the Policy Maker evaluate the models’ dashboard
5. The policy maker changes the status of the Policy to “EXTRACTED”

Figure 40. Policy extraction, receive policy response interaction diagram

5.4 Policy Evaluation

Feedback (opinions) from citizens affected by a policy is collected for policy evaluation and optimization.

1. The Policy Maker selects a Policy in “EXTRACTED” state
2. The Policy Maker creates a survey for the Policy specifying the survey type, questions, options and the output channel
3. The Policy Evaluation Component creates the survey and publish it on the selected channels
4. The relevant Stakeholders receive a notification and answer the survey on the specific channel
5. The Policy maker select an active survey a request the results
6. The Policy Evaluation Component close the survey and collect the feedbacks
7. The Policy Evaluation Component elaborates the result of the survey as a statistical score and eventually call the Text and Sentiment Analysis Component to evaluate a sentiment score
8. The Policy Maker evaluate the survey result and change the Policy status accordingly

Figure 41. Policy evaluation interaction diagram

5.5 Policy Presentation

A policy maker needs to understand the rationale behind the results of the forecast of a given policy (AI model), if the predictions were accurate, the contribution of each variable to the prediction, and their relationship. The steps the policy makes are:

1. The policy maker selects a model (e.g., based on regression) and a data set
2. A default interpretation dashboard is generated
3. The dashboard allows the user to browse the model performance, the features importance...
4. The policy maker browses the importance of different data features in the AI model.

The activity chart in Figure 42 shows this interaction and the components involved.

Figure 42. Policy Interpretation/Presentation interaction diagram

5.6 Datasets & Policy Sharing

A policy maker is aware of datasets for policies in different countries and wants to use them to run similar policies. The policy maker asks the data scientist to explore these data and train a model. The activity diagram in Figure 43 describes the components involved and the sequence of steps, summarised as:

1. The AI Expert browses the dataset catalogue and selects a dataset
2. The dataset is in a different language, the dataset is translated
3. The translated dataset is used to train a model

Figure 43. Datasets & Policy sharing interaction diagram

5.7 Reusing Datasets

A policy maker is aware of datasets for policies in different countries and wants to use them to run similar policies. The policy maker asks the data scientist to explore these data and train a model. The activity diagram in the next Figure 4444 describes the components involved and the sequence of steps, summarised as:

1. The data scientist explores the Dataset catalogue to find similar datasets
2. The selected dataset is used to train the model

Figure 44. Reusing datasets interaction diagram

5.8 Reusing Policy Definitions

A policy maker wants to define a new policy based on a previously created policy. The policy maker goes through the list of available policies to find the one that best fits the policy he/she wants to define, modifies the required fields and stores the new policy. The activity diagram in the next Figure 45 describes the components involved and the sequence of steps, summarised as:

1. The policy maker selects the policy from the Dataset and Policy Management component
2. Creates a new policy based on the selected one and modifies the required fields.
3. Stores the new defined policy.

Figure 45. Reusing Policy interaction diagram

6 Conclusions

This deliverable presents the second and last version of the AI4PublicPolicy Conceptual Model and Reference Architecture. This includes the description of the AI-based Policy Making Process, based on CRISP-DM methodology, the description of the main components and their interactions and the description of the cloud infrastructure. This deliverable is an updated version of deliverable D2.6 where the components' descriptions are updated, and their REST APIs identified. The interaction diagrams that define the usage of the AI4PublicPolicy platform have been updated after the first phase of the project has been completed and presented to the pilots.

Finally, the adherence of the RA to the Pilots User Stories collected in deliverable D2.1 and to the steps of the AI-based Policy Making Process is verified through a validation matrix and a set of scenarios.

7 References

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